

QUINOA FLOUR AS HYPOLIPIDEMIC AGENT IN MALE ALBINO RATS

EL SHARKAWY MONA. A², GEBRIL AHMED. Y¹, EBEID HAMADY. M¹, ALI SAFAA.E² and EL-HADIDY ESHAK. M²

¹Faculty of Agriculture, Ain Shams University, Egypt.

²Food Technology Recherche Institute, Agricultural Research Center, Egypt.

ABSTRACT

Quinoa (*Chenopodium quinoa*) seeds have gained a great interest in the last years, mainly due to its nutritional properties and its high content of good quality protein, oil and minerals. The result indicated in protein content was 12.9% on dry weight basis, while oil and ash content were 8.62% and 1.8%, respectively. The quinoa flour was rich in some amino acids as, Aspartic (0.93), Glutamic (1.69), Arginine (0.97), Leucine (0.72), and Lysine (0.64) g/100g protein, also quinoa flour was the highest content of oleic, linoleic and linolenic acid (2.52, 4.07 and 0.37g/100g oil, respectively).

The effect of diet containing quinoa seeds powder on hyperlipidemic rats was studied. This study (40 male albino rats) included that, the effect of quinoa flour (free gluten) on hyperglycemia albino rats (190±10g) divided to 5 groups. Group 1, rats were fed on basal diet contained corn flour normal group, while group 2 rats were fed on hyperlipidaemic group. Also, three groups were fed on diets contained 25% quinoa flour, 50% quinoa, 75% quinoa flour, respectively. Results indicated that rats fed on 75% quinoa flour the higher decrease in cholesterol level than diet 25% quinoa flour and hyperlipidemic group. Also, rats fed on different percent of quinoa flour showed a significant decrease in LDL compared with hyperlipidemic group. In contrast, there are no significant differences between the 3 groups fed on gradually percentage of quinoa flour compared with hyperlipidemic group. In parallel, there is significant difference in LDL content between diet fed on 50% quinoa flour and diet fed on 75% quinoa flour. Also, rats' groups fed on different quinoa flour showed a significant decrease in AST and ALT activity compared to that of hyperlipidemic group. Results observed in rats group fed on 75% quinoa flour had the highest decrease in ALT activity compared with rats group fed on hyperlipidemic group and other groups. Conclusively, quinoa flour act as a hyperlipidemic agents may due to omega fatty acids and branched chain amino acids ratios.

Keywords: quinoa flour, free gluten, hypolipidemic

INTRODUCTION

Quinoa grains have an established excellent nutritional food quality and were also called “the mother grain”. Quinoa is one of the oldest crops in the Andean Region, with approximately 7000 years of cultivation history, great cultures like the Incas and Tiahuanacu had domesticated and conserved this ancient crop (Jacobsen, 2003). Bilal is et al, (2019) showed that quinoa is well adapted to a wide range of climatic conditions and has significant potential for increased production as a new crop in the Mediterranean region and in other parts of the world, including northern Europe, North America, Asia, and Africa. Quinoa is a complete food with high-nutritional value due mainly to its high content of good quality protein. Besides protein content, many studies have been made of their lipids, starch, minerals and

saponins it also contains minerals and vitamins like vitamin B, vitamin C and vitamin E. Quinoa flour is low in gluten due the low contents of prolamins and glutamines. It is usually used to enhance baking flours in the preparation of biscuits, noodles, and pastries, and for the preparation of baked foods to maintain the moisture and give an agreeable flavor **Nisar et al, (2017)**. **Abdelazim, (2018)** found that, the proximate analysis showed that the quinoa flour in both of 2 year and quinoa flat bread contained 14.73% and 13.09% crude protein, 6.51% and 8.66% ether extract, 2.83% 4.52% total ash, 4.15% and 5.96% crude fiber , 60.28% and 49.67% carbohydrate and 358.63% and 328.98 (Kcal./100g) Energy on dry weight. Quinoa flour had great amino acid balance with higher total essential amino acids (TEAA) 34.72, Phenylalanine + Tyrosine 6.09, Leucine 5.95 and lysine 5.42g/100g protein, but the contents of total non-essential amino acids (TNEAA) 39.66, glutamic 12.19, glycine 8.22 and aspartic 6.55g/100g protein.

The aim of this experiment, study the relationship between bioactive components in quinoa flour and hyperlipidemic diseases.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Prepare raw material

Dry Quinoa variety (*Chenopodium quinoa*) was obtained from Crops Research Institute, Agricultural Research Center. Cholesterol, cellulose, casein, vitamins and minerals were obtained from Al-Gamhoria Pharmaceutical Company, Cairo, Egypt. Corn oil and starch were obtained from the local market. Forty adult male albino rats (Sprague-Dawley) were obtained from the laboratory animal colony. Weighting were approximately between (190 ± 10g). Kits used to determine serum cholesterol, triglycerides, HDL, uric acid, urea nitrogen and creatinine by Alkan Chemical Company, Cairo, Egypt. While, LDL and v-LDL were calculated.

METHODS

Preparation of quinoa flour:

Quinoa flour was prepared comply to **Al Shehry (2016)** procedure. Quinoa seeds were cleaned and washed cold water followed by 15 minutes soaked to remove saponin then dried on a plate in an air oven at 50°C. The dried seeds were ground over night to find powder in an electric grinder stainless using laboratorial disc mill into flour that could pass through a 60mesh screen and save powder in polyethylene paper bags.

Determination of moisture content:

The moisture content of quinoa flour was determined as described in **A.O.A.C (2015)**. Five grams of homogenized sample were dried in a hot air oven at 105°C till a constant weight.

Determination of ash:

Ash content was determined according to **A.O.A.C (2015)**. Two grams of each sample were placed in silica crucible and ignited at 550°C in a muffle furnace till constant weight, and then the percentage of ash content was calculated.

Determination of crude fiber content:

Fiber content in sample was determined as described by **Kirk and Sawyer (1991)**.

Determination of crude protein:

Total nitrogen was determined by micro kjeldahl method according to **A.O.A.C (2015)**. The crude protein was calculated by multiplying the total nitrogen content by the factor (6.25) for all cereals except wheat was (5.75).

Determination of total lipids:

Total lipids were determined according to the method of **A.O.A.C (2015)**.

Determination of ether extract:

Crude fat was extracted using petroleum ether (40-60°C) in a Soxhlet apparatus. The extractable crude fat was estimated following the procedure described by **A.O.A.C (2015)**.

Determination of Total carbohydrates:

Total carbohydrates content of samples was calculated by difference as mentioned by **Fraser and Holmes (1959)**.

Energy calculation:

Total calories of 100g quinoa flour was calculated by the formula of **James (1995)**.

Total Calories = (Oil X9 + Protein X4 + Total carbohydrate X4).

Fatty acids profiles by GC:

The methyl esters of fatty acids, and standard compounds were analyzed by using HP 6890 GC capillary column gas liquid chromatography with a dual flame ionized were carried out on (30m x 0.32 mm x 0.25 µm) DB- 225 capillary column, stationary phase (50 % cyanopropyl phenyl + 50% dimethyl polydioxanone). Column temperature: initial temperature was 150°C; the temperature was programmed by increasing the temperature from 150- 170°C at the rate of 10°C/minute, holding three minutes. The injector and detector temperature were 230°C and 250 °C, respectively. Carrier gas: Hydrogen flow rate 40 ml /minute, and air flow rate was 450 ml /minute. Peak identifications were established by comparing the retention times obtain with standard methyl esters. The areas under the chromatographic peak were measured with electronic integrator (**ISO method 2011**).

Determination of amino acids content by HPLC:

Amino acids composition in quinoa flour was estimated as described by the **A.O.A.C (2015)**.

Design of experimental animals:

After feeding on basal diet for one week, rats were divided into two major groups. The first main group (8 rats) was fed on the basal diet for another 5 weeks and was considered as normal control group. The second main groups (32 rats) were fed hyperlipidemic diet for two weeks (10% sheep tail fat and 1% cholesterol + 0.25% bile salt) they divided into three (3) sub groups. The first sub group fed on hyperlipidemic diet until the end of the experiment and considered as hyperlipidemic control. The second subgroup (8rats) was fed basal diet containing 25% quinoa flour given daily. The third subgroup (8 rats) was fed basal diet containing 50% quinoa flour given daily. The fourth subgroup (8 rats) was fed on basal diet containing 75% quinoa flour orally given daily **Martin- Carronm et al., (1999)**.

Diet composition and animal groups:

Diet composition: Basal diet was prepared according to **Reeves et al. (1993)**. Also, the vitamins and minerals mixture have the prepared according to **(Campbell, 1963)**. While, Hyperlipidemic diets content was prepared by **(Hassarajani et al.,2007)**.

Serum Sampling:

Blood sampling were collected after 12hour fasting at the end of the experiment (after fed on experimental diet). Using the retro- orbital into a dry clean centrifugal tube and left to clot in a water bath (25°C) at room temperature for half an hour. The blood was centrifuged for 10 minutes at 3000 rpm to separate serum the reminder was carefully aspirated and transferred into clear quit fit plastic tubes and kept frozen at (-20°C) until analysis.

Biochemical analyses of serum:

Determination of lipids profile:

Triglycerides were determined according to **Fassati and Prencipe (1982)**. Total cholesterol and HDL were determined according to the methods described by **Allain (1974)**. LDL was determined according to the method of **Lee and Nieman (1996)**.

$LDL \text{ (mg/dl)} = \text{Total cholesterol} - (\text{HDL} + \text{VLDL})$.

$VLDL \text{ (mg/dl)} = \text{Triglycerides} \div 5$.

Determination of kidney functions:

Uric acid and creatinine were determined according to the method of **While et al. (1970)** and **Henry (1974)**, respectively.

Determination of Liver functions:

Alanine aminotransferase (ALT), aspartate aminotransferase (AST) and alkaline phosphatase (ALP) were determined according to the method of **Tiez (1979) ; Henry (1974) and Moss (1982)**, respectively.

Statistical analysis

All analyses were performed using three replications. The obtained data from each treatment in respect to different parameters during storage were subjected to analysis of variance (ANOVA), with treatment and storage time as sources of variation. Tukey's HSD (Honestly significant difference) test was carried out at a significance level of $P \leq 0.05$ to ascertain significant differences between the means. All analyses were performed using the SPSS software package (Version 19.0 for Windows 2000; SPSS Inc., Chicago, IL, USA)

Results and Discussion

Chemical constituents of quinoa dried seeds

Quinoa seed powder (QSP) was analysed base on dry weight characteristics. The moisture, fat, protein, ash, total carbohydrates and crude fibre (g/100g) were 10.50, 6.62, 14.9, 2.8, 65.7 and 2.7%, respectively (Table 1).

Table 1: Chemical composition of raw materials (% on dry weight basis)

Constituents %	Quinoa seeds(%DW)
Moisture	10.50± 1.23
Crude Protein	14.90 ± 0.95
Crude fat	6.62 ± 0.74
Ash	2.80 ± 0.32
Crude Fibre	2.70± 0.85
*Total Carbohydrate	65.70 ± 9.80
Energy (Kcal.)	391.98 ± 14.63

Means± standard deviations.

The chemical composition of quinoa seeds under investigation was found in Table (1). It could be noticed that the moisture content of the raw material was low (13.28%). While, crude protein content was high in dried quinoa seeds (12.90). As for crude fibre of dried quinoa was low content (4.07). Also, the total energy 391.98 kcal in 100 g dried quinoa. Also, dried quinoa seed was low content of (1.80) ash. These data are parallel to results in **Nisar et al, (2017)** and **Abdelazim, (2018)**.

Fatty acid composition of quinoa seeds powder:

The relative percentage of the fatty acids was determined by G.C for quinoa oil. The results are illustrated in Table (2).

Table 2: Fatty acid composition of quinoa seeds powder

Component of fatty acid	Quinoa seeds powder
Saturated Fatty acid	Palmitic acid 9.94
	Eicosenoic acid 1.8
	Stearic acid 0.14
	Arachidic acid 0.46
	Behenic acid 0.59
Mono- unsaturated Fatty acid (MUFA)	Oleic acid 29.3
	Erucic acid 1.7
Poly-unsaturated Fatty acid (PUFA)	Linoleic acid 47.31
	α -Linolenic acid 4.36
Total unsaturated Fatty acid	12.63
Total monounsaturated Fatty acid	31
Total polyunsaturated Fatty acid	51.67
LA/ALA	10.85
n3: n6	1:10

Lipids are concentrated sources of energy as well as structural components of cell membranes that the body uses for performing a variety of normal functions. A higher intake of vegetables is associated with a reduced risk of type 2 diabetes, due to their high unsaturated fat content, which is associated with lower inflammation. The quality of lipids is very important. For example, it is known that omega-6 stimulates inflammatory activity in the body, while omega-3 performs anti-inflammatory functions. A lower ratio of omega-6 omega-3 fatty acids is more desirable for reducing the risk of cardiovascular diseases. Quinoa flour is rich in palmitic acid (9.94%) as unsaturated fatty acid while it is high contents of oleic acid and linoleic acid (29.3% and 47.3%) flour respectively **Altuna et al., (2018)**. EFAs can be grouped in two families called omega 3 (ω -3) and omega 6 (ω -6) Linoleic acid (omega 6) is the polyunsaturated fatty acid most abundant in quinoa oil in this study.

Table 3: Amino acid composition of quinoa seeds powder (g/100g)

Amino acids	FAO*	Quinoa seeds powder
Non-Essential Amino Acids (NEAA)		
Aspartic		0.93
Serine		0.48
Glutamic acid		1.69
Glycine		0.62
Alanine		0.61
Arginine		0.97
Cystine	0.6	0.13
Proline		0.40
Tyrosine	-	0.40
Essential Amino Acids (EAA)		
Valine	3.9	0.54
Threonine	-	0.40
Leucine	3.9	0.72
Phenylalanine	3.8	0.48
Histidine	1.5	0.32
Lysine	4.5	0.64
Isoleucine	-	0.44
Methionine	1.6	0.20
Arginine: Lysine	1.52	
Methionine: Glycine	2.58	
Valine: Leucine: Isoleucine	1: 1: 1	

* Suggested composition for aromatic amino acids Phe + Tyr (FAO, 2020).

Amino acids profile included essential amino acids (leucine, lysine, valine, isoleucine, phenylalanine, threonine, histidine, methionine, and tryptophan) and non-essential amino acids (glutamic acid, aspartic acid, arginine, glycine, alanine, tyrosine, and cysteine) are shown in table (3).

Results indicated that quinoa flour was high content in glutamic acid (1.69%) followed by arginine (0.97%) and aspartic acid (0.93%) as nonessential amino acids. Also, its high contents in leucine and lysine (0.72 and 0.64, respectively). While quinoa flour was lowest content in methionine then cystine (0.20 and 0.13). Arginine: lysine ratio might be the major factor for causing a change in cholesterol of rabbits given different dietary protein (1.52). Also, the Arg: lys ratio is very effective in regulating the triglycerides level in serum. Indeed, rats fed the legume seeds showed higher serum Arg: lys ratio than those offered casein Diet. Morita et al., (1997) added that the cholesterol-lowering effects of soy bean, rice and potato protein were correlated with their Met concentration or Met: Gly ratio. They added no direct

explanation for the mechanism of the effect of Met on cholesterol metabolism, in contrast to Met which is hypercholesterolemic in rats, fed a cholesterol-free diet (Saeki and Kiriyama, 1990). These data are adapted by results in table (3), its showed that the higher ratio in Meth: Glycine (2.58) than Arg.: Lys (1.52). While, the ratio of valine: leucine: isoleucine as a Branched Chain Amino Acid are importance to lipid metabolism in liver (Campollo et al., 1992). Therefore, this study observed the importance to determinate the Branched chain Amino Acid in quinoa flour, especially its rich in protein content. In quinoa flour, this ratio was 1:1:1, it complies with Park et al., (2020).

Table 4: Changes in rats body weight fed on different Formulae contained quinoa flour (mg).

Groups Parameters	Normal group	Hyperlipidaemic group	diet contained 25% quinoa flour	diet contained 50% quinoa flour	Diet contained 75% quinoa flour
Zero time	195.87 ^{ab*} ±18.90	209.62 ^a ±23.96	201.00 ^{ab} ±9.52	198.00 ^b ±11.61	196.00 ^b ±15.55
One week	189.12 ^b ±20.21	199.75 ^b ±21.74	200.00 ^{ab} ±12.60	203.87 ^{ab} ±26.55	194.87 ^b ±15.96
Two weeks	190.37 ^b ±13.18	198.87 ^b ±20.03	206.25 ^{ab} ±18.29	208.37 ^{ab} ±18.45	203.12 ^{ab} ±10.97
Three weeks	183.87 ^c ±6.99	199.62 ^b ±20.32	208.62 ^{ab} ±21.61	214.00 ^{ab} ±22.07	217.50 ^a ±14.91
Four weeks	182.25 ^c ±8.36	202.45 ^{ab} ±16.46	213.62 ^{ab} ±20.38	220.12 ^{ab} ±18.62	222.50 ^a ±12.15
Five weeks	182.42 ^c ±14.20	212.75 ^{ab} ±15.07	225.55 ^a ±18.43	227.34 ^a ±15.92	231.50 ^a ± 17.40
Six weeks	183.33 ^c ±17.24	213.83 ^{ab} ±22.01	226.45 ^a ±19.35	229.22 ^a ±22.23	232.48 ^a ±18.90
Increments of body weight	-6.40	2.00	12.66	15.65	18.60

*All results are expressed as means ±SD. Values in each row which have different letters are significantly different (p<0.05).

**Zero time after rats fed on hyperlipidemic diet during experimental period

Results in table (4) rats body weight fed on basal diet were gradually decrease significant (from 195.87 to 183.33 g), while the body weight in hyperlipidemic group fed on basal diet was increased (from 209.62 to 213.83g). While, the percentage of increment in body weight in rats fed of basal diet contained 25, 50 and 75% quinoa flour were 12.66, 15.62 and 18.60%, respectively. The highest increase in body weight in rats fed on diet contained 75% quinoa. The increment in body weight may due to the high content of protein in quinoa flour (12.90%).

Mona S. Hala by et al, (2017) results could be summarized that diet fortified at 30% and 40% quinoa seeds powder can improved the body weight gain, feed consumption, feed efficiency ratio, reduced blood cholesterol and other lipids.

Table 5: Changes in the serum cholesterol in rats fed on different Formulae contained quinoa flour (mg/dl).

Parameters Groups	Zero time	After 2 weeks	After 4 weeks	After 6 weeks
Normal group	*79.90 ^d ±2.78	73.83 ^d ±10.83	74.50 ^d ±16.68	71.00 ^d ±6.48
Hyperlipidaemic group	189.00 ^a ±32.91	178.50 ^{ab} ±14.9	181.82 ^b ±13.20	155.83 ^{bc} ±10.72
diet contained 25% quinoa flour	182.83 ^b ±12.72	175.70 ^{ab} ±5.42	165.83 ^c ±11.18	158.50 ^{bc} ±10.07
diet contained 50% quinoa flour	185.16 ^a ±9.72	179.83 ^b ±7.08	173.54 ^{ab} ±4.62	150.00 ^{bc} ±8.65
diet contained 75% quinoa flour	180.67 ^b ±4.38	172.82 ^{ab} ±5.40	164.67 ^c ±12.59	138.33 ^{bc} ±6.79

*All results are expressed as means ±SD. Values in each row which have different letters are significantly different (p<0.05).

**Zero time after rats fed on hyperlipidemic diet during experimental period

Results in table (5) indicated that, the effect of different concentration of quinoa flour (25, 50, and 75, respectively) on serum cholesterol. Data showed gradually decrease significant in serum cholesterol in all group. While rats fed on diet containing 75% quinoa flour were the high least significant decrease in serum cholesterol (from 180.67 to 138.33) followed by rats fed on diet containing 50% (from 185.16 to 150.00) then rats fed on diet containing 25% quinoa (from 182.83 to 158.50). Also, the end of experiment, the decrement percentage in serum cholesterol was 23.42, 18.99, and 13.31% respectively. Compared to hyperlipidemic group which rats fed on basal diet the decrement percentage was 5.38.

The results of Oliveira Silva et al., (2018), showed beneficial effects of the intake of quinoa with a significant reduction in total cholesterol, triglycerides and LDL-c. They added that Quinoa is a gluten-free pseudo cereal with high biological value protein, low glycaemic carbohydrates, phytosterols and omega-3 and omega-6 fatty acids.

Table 6: Changes in the serum triglycerides of rats fed on different formula contained quinoa flour (mg/dl).

Parameters Groups	Zero time	After 2 weeks	After 4 weeks	After 6 weeks
Normal group	68.35 ^d ± 9.65	63.33 ^{cd} ±13.20	60.33±37.87	54.83 ^e ±10.22
Hyperlipidaemic group	90.34 ^b ± 8.22	88.17 ^b ±7.73	84.50 ^{ab} ±10.48	81.95 ^{ab} ±8.73
Basal diet contained 25% quinoa flour	93.84 ^a ± 14.55	82.83 ^{ab} ±6.45	78.50 ^c ±2.41	63.50 ^{cd} ±3.62
Basal diet contained 50% quinoa flour	97.28 ^a ± 9.74	78.17 ^c ±10.79	71.67 ^d ±14.40	60.67 ^{cd} ±12.96
Basal diet contained 75% quinoa flour	95.08 ^a ± 11.40	80.00 ^{ab} ±10.82	69.17 ^d ±12.34	53.83 ^e ±3.30

*All results are expressed as means \pm SD. Values in each row which have different letters are significantly different ($p < 0.05$).

**Zero time after rats fed on hyperlipidaemic diet during experimental period

Table (6) showed that, after fed on hyperlipidaemic diet the TG concentration in different diets rang from 93.83 to 97.28 mg/dl compared to normal group which fed on basal diet (68.35 mg/dl).

At the same trend, rats fed on diet containing quinoa flour were gradually decreased significant in TG by increasing quinoa flour concentration during 6 weeks. Also, after 6 weeks, the highest increase significant in TG was observed in rats group fed on 75% quinoa flour (from 95.08 to 53.83 mg/dl) compared to zero time. While, the TG decrease in rats group fed on 25% was nearly compared to rats group fed on diet containing 50% (63.50 and 60.67 mg/dl), respectively.

Table7: Changes in the total lipid (TL) of rats fed on different formula contained quinoa flour (mg/dl).

Parameters Groups	Zero time	After 2 weeks	After 4 weeks	After 6 weeks
Normal group	238.26 ^d \pm 17.72	336.33 ^b \pm 18.11	230.00 ^b \pm 14.26	227.00 ^b \pm 18.06
Hyperlipidaemic group	249.00 ^b \pm 18.56	290.00 ^a \pm 18.56	284.00 ^a \pm 19.16	275.23 ^{ab} \pm 17.16
diet contained 25% quinoa flour	241.43 ^c \pm 17.25	269.66 ^b \pm 18.17	251.43 ^{bc} \pm 16.80	246.33 ^{bc} \pm 19.52
diet contained 50% quinoa flour	236.52 ^d \pm 15.30	264.33 ^b \pm 12.51	254.50 ^b \pm 13.48	240.52 ^c \pm 18.40
diet contained 75% quinoa flour	280.67 ^a \pm 17.64	273.14 ^b \pm 17.20	263.84 ^b \pm 16.93	253.20 ^{bc} \pm 19.81

*All results are expressed as means \pm SD. Values in each row which have different letters are significantly different ($p < 0.05$).

**Zero time after rats fed on hyperlipidaemic diet during experimental period

Table (7) found the TL concentration during 6 weeks on rats fed on diet contain 25,50,75% quinoa flour .At the end of experiment, the decrease significantly in TL was observed in rats fed on diet contain quinoa flour , it was ranged from 240.52 to 253.20 mg/dl compared to hyperlipidaemic group 275.23. Rats fed on diet contain 75% quinoa flour were higher decrease significant in TL.

Generally, all groups fed on different formula contained quinoa flour were decrease in TL, TG, and TC by different level. The decrement effect of quinoa flour on lipids profile may due to the bioactive components content in quinoa flour as poly cyclic aromatic amino acid and PUFA.

Table 8: Effect of quinoa flour formula on serum HDL, LDL, v-LDL(mg/dl).

Parameters Groups	HDL	LDL	v-LDL	Risk ratio
Normal group	107.17 ^a ±9.64	26.17 ^c ±2.80	10.77 ^c ±0.87	0.24 ^d ±0.02
Hyperlipidaemic group	69.33 ^c ±7.45	43.33 ^a ±3.31	14.53 ^a ±1.02	0.62 ^a ±0.10
Basal diet contained 25% quinoa flour	78.17 ^b ±3.91	39.17 ^{ab} ±2.07	12.13 ^{ab} ±0.90	0.50 ^{ab} ±0.08
Basal diet contained 50% quinoa flour	82.67 ^b ±4.88	38.00 ^b ±2.28	11.09 ^{2b} ±	0.46 ^b ±0.04
Basal diet contained 75% quinoa flour	91.67 ^{ab} ±3.91	31.50 ^b ±3.46	10.97 ^b ±0.80	0.34 ^c ±0.08

*All results are expressed as means ±SD. Values in each column which have different letters are significantly different (p<0.05).

**Zero time after rats fed on hyperlipidaemic diet during experimental period

The increase of HDL by increase in quinoa flour content in diets were showed in table (8) compared to hyperlipidaemic group. The highest increase in HDL was observant in rats fed on diet containing 75% quinoa flour (91.67 mg/dl) compared to serum HDL hyperlipidaemic group (69.33 mg/dl). In contrast, the level of LDL was gradually decrease significant (39.17, 38.00, and 31.50) which increase in quinoa flour concentration in the different formula compared to LDL hyperlipidaemic group (26.17 mg/dl) these results, reflected to risk ratio. Results in the same table indicated that the highest significant decrease in rats group fed on 75% followed by 50% and 25% quinoa flour (0.34, 0.46, and 0.50), respectively compared to hyperlipidaemic group (0.62). Generally, the risk ratio in rats group fed on different concentration of quinoa flour was significant decrease in risk ratio compered to hyperlipidaemic group. In parallel to LDL serum v- LDL in rats fed on quinoa flour was significant decrease gradually by increase the content of quinoa flour in diet. It's observed that no significant variance between rats fed on diet containing 75% quinoa flour compared to rats. In normal group which are fed on basal diet only (10.97 and 10.77mg/dl), respectively.

These data were adapted by Liangkui Li et al, (2018). They found that, after 4 weeks of intervention, blood glucose and low-density lipoprotein (LDL) cholesterol were significantly lower than baseline in both groups but there was no difference between quinoa and control. Influence of quinoa seed flour on lipid profile of hyperlipidaemic rats: The influence of QSP on lipid profile in the rats from each group, is presented in Tables (5,6 and7). It is noted that the positive control group, when fed using a basal diet, which contained 2% cholesterol, experienced a statistically significant increase (P< 0.05) in the mean values of TC, TG, LDL-C, and VLDL-C (), compared with the control negative group, which was fed the basal diet only (respectively). On the contrary, HDL-C facilitates catabolism, by helping

to transport excess cholesterol out of the peripheral tissue, and into the liver. Furthermore, our results closely correspond to those of **Wang et al., (2012)**. Indicated that the increase in HDL-C ratio is one of the most significant identifiers for any anti-hypercholesterolemia agent. Rats which were fed a high-cholesterol diet with two various levels from quinoa seeds powder fortified at 35% & 45%, had lower mean values of lipid profile compared with the positive control group. This might be as a direct result of reduced absorption of cholesterol, when accompanied by an increase in faecal bile acid and excretion of cholesterol, which is attributed to the dietary supplementation. In fact, the best results in lipid fractions for all treated groups was noticed in the group fed on a high cholesterol diet fortified with quinoa seeds powder at 45%, because this treatment improved levels of serum cholesterol and triglycerides. These findings closely correspond to the previous researches of **Farinazzi et al., (2012)** and **Zevallos, et al., (2014)**.

Table 9: Effect of different quinoa flour formula on serum ALT during 6 weeks (IUL/L)

Parameters Groups	Zero time	After2 weeks	After4 weeks	After6 weeks
Normal group	33.83 ^{*d} ±2.64	34.83 ^d ±1.47	33.17 ^d ±2.71	32.25 ^d ±2.69
Hyperlipidaemic group	75.00 ^a ±3.85	73.83 ^a ±2.79	71.17 ^a ±3.06	71.12 ^a ±3.04
Basal diet contained 25% quinoa flour	70.17 ^b ±2.79	64.83 ^c ±3.32	64.67 ^c ±1.63	62.77 ^c ±2.56
Basal diet contained 50% quinoa flour	68.33 ^c ±2.50	60.67 ^c ±2.73	58.17 ^{cd} ±5.27	57.33 ^{cd} ±5.18
Basal diet contained 75% quinoa flour	72.50 ^c ±2.43	60.50 ^c ±1.87	56.67 ^{cd} ±2.58	55.65 ^{cd} ±2.50

*All results are expressed as means ±SD. Values in each row which have different letters are significantly different (p<0.05).

**Zero time after rats fed on hyperlipidaemic diet during experimental period.

Liver enzyme as ALT and AST are a mirror of reflected to hepato- activity, therefore, table (9) discussed the ALT activity change during rats fed on diet containing after 6 weeks. ALT level was gradually decrease in ALT in rats' groups fed on diet containing 25, 50, 75% quinoa flour (163.98, 59.89, and 53.87 IUL/L, respectively) compared to ALT level in hyperlipidaemic group (70.03 IUL/L). The highest decrease in ALT level in rats' group was fed on diet containing 75% quinoa flour followed by diet 50% and 25%.

Table10: Effect of different quinoa flour formula on serum AST during 6 weeks (IUL/L)

Parameters Groups	Zero time	After2 weeks	After4 weeks	After6 weeks
Normal group	44.17 ^{c*} ±4.62	45.17 ^c ±2.14	43.00 ^c ±2.89	42.89 ^c ±2.66
Hyperlipidaemic group	78.50 ^a ±2.34	75.17 ^{ab} ±5.60	72.83 ^b ±3.06	70.03 ^b ±2.95
Basal diet contained 25% quinoa flour	74.67 ^{ab} ±4.27	68.50 ^{bc} ±3.21	66.00 ^{bc} ±3.95	63.98 ^c ±3.53
Basal diet contained 50% quinoa flour	72.67 ^b ±5.78	64.00 ^{bc} ±2.83	61.00 ^c ±4.98	59.89 ^d ±4.05
Basal diet contained 75% quinoa flour	69.50 ^{bc} ±3.67	60.33 ^c ±3.20	59.00 ^d ±2.83	53.87±2.67

*All results are expressed as means ±SD. Values in each row which have different letters are significantly different (p<0.05).

**Zero time after rats fed on hyperlipidaemic diet during experimental period.

In parallel, results in table 10 indicated that gradually Decrease significant in AST during feeding period (6 weeks). After 6 weeks, the highest decrease significant in rats group fed on diets containing 75% quinoa flour (55.65 IU/L) followed by rats fed on diets containing 50% and 25% quinoa flour (57.33 and 62.77 IU/L, respectively) compared to rats fed on hyperlipidaemic diet (71.12 IU/L). Also, results showed that, gradually decrease significant in all groups fed on diets containing different quinoa flour percentage from zero time to 6 weeks.

Table11. Effect of feeding on Quinoa seeds flour on uric acid, urea and creatinine (mg/dl)

Kidneyfunctions Groups	Uric acid	Urea	Creatinine
Normal group	0.97 ^{*b} ±0.19	14.83 ^c ±3.49	0.62 ^b ±0.07
Hyperlipidaemic group	1.20 ^a ±0.14	30.17 ^a ±3.97	0.72 ^a ±0.09
Basal diet contained 25% quinoa flour	1.10 ^{ab} ±0.30	27.67 ^{ab} ±3.61	0.68 ^{ab} ±0.08
Basal diet contained 50% quinoa flour	1.02 ^{ab} ±0.23	20.17 ^b ±2.56	0.65 ^{ab} ±0.03
Basal diet contained 75% quinoa flour	0.91 ^b ±0.15	17.50 ^{bc} ±7.77	0.63 ^{ab} ±0.06

*All results are expressed as means \pm SD. Values in each column which have different letters are significantly different ($p < 0.05$).

**Zero time after rats fed on hyperlipidaemic diet during experimental period.

Serum Uric acid was the highly decrease significant in rats fed on diet which containing 75% followed by 50% than 25% (0.91, 1.02, and 1.10 mg/dL, respectively) compared to rats fed on hyperlipidaemic diet (1.20 mg/dL). In Parallel, data observed the gradually decrease significant in serum urea (27.67, 20.17 and 17.50mg/dL) and serum creatinine (0.68, 0.65 and 0.63 mg/dL) when increase quinoa flour percentage in diets. Generally, rats fed on diet containing 75% quinoa flour was better than other rats' groups.

Conclusively, the quinoa flour as a free gluten seeds may decrease the serum lipids, triglycerides, cholesterol, LDL, HDL and v-LDL. These results due to the bioactive components in quinoa flour as Omega fatty acids and Branched chain amino acids.

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